

MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF EYE BOWL INDEX OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *In children of junior school age, the growth of the eyeball in the longitudinal and transverse directions does not occur simultaneously, but alternately. As a result, children's eyeballs appear in different types at different stages of the school age period.*

Keywords: *eyeball index, eyeball height, eyeball width, hameconchia, mesoconchia, gypsiconchia.*

INTRODUCTION

Studying the physical development of children living in Izboskan district, which is a unique geographical zone, is of both theoretical and practical importance. In this direction, the study of changes in anthropometric parameters of children of junior school age is one of the most urgent issues.

The purpose of the study. The purpose of the research is to observe the dynamics of the growth of the morphometric indicators of the eyeball index in boys and girls of junior school age, to study the periods of formation, the laws of growth and development, and to identify early cases of lagging behind physical development (in the case of children of primary school age (7-12 years old) living in Izboskan district of Andijan region).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

180 physically and mentally healthy boys and girls of elementary school age (7-12 years old) living in Izboskan district were taken as the material of the research.

The width of the eyeball - this indicator is of two types: the maxillofrontal width of the eyeball and the dacryal width of the eyeball (L.I. Tegako, I.I. Sullivan, 1989).

Some researchers say (A.D. Dzhagaryan, 1984) that this indicator is equal to the distance between the zygomolare-ectoconchion points. To determine this indicator, we took the width of the intermediate distance from the maxillofrontal (mf) point of the eyeball to the middle of the posterior edge of the eyeball. We measured this indicator with a barbell circle.

In craniometry, measurement of the left orbit is accepted (Ya.Ya. Roginsky, M.G. Levin, 1978). Therefore, all craniometric examinations of the eye socket were performed on the left eye socket.

The height of the eyeball is the distance from the middle of the upper edge of the eyeball to the middle of the lower edge of the eyeball. We measured this indicator with a barbell.

Eyeball index - eyeball height*100the width of the eye socket

RESULTS

Depending on the eyeball index, the orbit is divided into three types: up to 75.9 - low eyeball (hameconchia), from 76.0 to 84.9 - middle eyeball (mesoconchia), 85.0 and above - high eyeball which is called z cup (hypsiconchia).

If the index of the eye cup increases intensively in boys under the age of 7-10 years, then it decreases. In girls, the index of the eye cup increases between the ages of 7-11, and it can be seen to decrease at the age of 12. The indicator of the index of the eyeball is of the hemoconchic type in both sexes aged 7-12 years.

Figure 1. The field of measurement of the width and height of the eyeball
Width of the 1st eye socket; Height of the 2nd eye socket

Table 1
Growth dynamics of morphometric indicators of eye cup index of children of junior school
age (in $X \pm m$, cm)

Child's age	Gender	Craniometric parameters
		Eye bowl index
7 years old	Boy	79,34
	Girl	77,94
8 years old	Boy	79,24
	Girl	77,52
9 years old	Boy	82,12
	Girl	78,64
10 years old	Boy	82,72
	Girl	78,14
11 years old	Boy	81,06
	Girl	78,22
12 years old	Boy	79,24
	Girl	76,10

CONCLUSION

In children of junior school age, the growth of the eyeball in the longitudinal and transverse directions does not occur at the same time, but takes place alternately. As a result, children's eyeballs appear in different types at different stages of the school age period.

REFERENCES

1. Avtandilov G. G. Medical morphometry. - M.: Medicine, 1990. - 384 p. (in Russ).
2. Alekseev V.P. Osteometry. - M.: Nauka, 1966. - 250 p. (in Russ).
3. Alekseev V.P., Debets G.F. Craniometry. Methodology of anthropological studies - M.: Nauka, 1964. - 127 p. (in Russ).
4. Atakhanov A.A. Craniometric parameters of high school age children living in Asaka District, Andijan Region. / Dissertation. Andijan-2015. (in Uzb)
5. Atakhonov A.A., Khatamov A.I., Ulugbekova G.J. Craniometric indicators of the facial part of the head in school-age children living in Asaka district of Andijan region. Uzbekistan therapy newsletter. - 2015. No. 3, p. 84-86. (in Uzb)
6. Dzhagaryan A.D. External facial morphology and plastic reconstruction. - Yerevan: Publishing house. Academy of Sciences of the Armenian SSR, 1984. - p. 22-33. (in Russ).
7. Raimjanov R.R. Craniometric indicators of children of small school age living in Andijan district of Andijan region. / Dissertation. Andijan, 2014. (in Uzb)
8. Roginsky Ya.Ya., Levin M.G. Anthropology. - M.: Higher School, 1978. - 527 p. (in Russ).
9. Sinelnikov R.D., Sinelnikov Ya.R. Atlas anatomy human 1 volume. - M.: Medicine, 1996. - 343 p. (in Russ).
10. Tegako L.I., Salivon I.I. Fundamentals of modern anthropology. - Minsk: Universitetskoe, 1989. - p. 39-81. (in Russ).
11. Tishevsky I.A. Adult and constitutional anthropology. // Flying. posobie. - Chelyabinsk: Izd-vo YuUrGU, 2000. - 56 p. (in Russ).
12. Kharitonov V.M., Ojigova A.P., Godina E. Z. Anthropology. // Uchebnik dlya vuzov. - Vlados, 2004. - 272 c. (in Russ).
13. Shokirov H.U. Craniometric indicators of small school-age children living in Andijan city, Andijan region // Master's thesis. Andijan-2017. (in Uzb)
14. <https://www.ziyonet.uz>
15. <https://www.dissercat.com>
16. <https://elibrary.ru>